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AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE JOINT EFFECTS OF EXCHANGE RATE DEVALUATION AND MONETARY POLICY TIGHTENING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA

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DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496207>

Abstract: This study empirically investigates the joint effects of exchange rate devaluation and monetary policy tightening on the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria over the period 1980 to 2024. SMEs play a critical role in employment generation, income distribution, and economic diversification; however, they remain highly vulnerable to macroeconomic shocks, particularly those stemming from currency fluctuations and restrictive monetary regimes. The study adopts a time series econometric approach, employing the Ordinary Least Square and the Cochrane Orcutt to find the relationships between SME performance and key macroeconomic variables, including exchange rate, monetary policy rate (MPR), inflation rate, real interest rate, and credit to the private sector. Stationarity tests using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron procedures confirm that all variables are integrated of order zero, justifying their use in level form. Descriptive statistics reveal considerable volatility in exchange rate and inflation, suggesting an unstable macroeconomic environment. Empirical results show that exchange rate devaluation significantly constrains SME performance by increasing input costs, particularly for imported goods and capital. Likewise, monetary policy tightening reflected in high interest and policy rates adversely affects SME access to finance, stifling growth and innovation. Inflation and real interest rates further exacerbate these constraints, while credit to the private sector offers a mitigating effect when sufficiently expanded. The findings underscore the need for balanced macroeconomic policies that stabilize the currency and ensure affordable credit conditions for SMEs. Policy recommendations include targeted intervention funds, exchange rate management strategies, and SME-friendly monetary frameworks to cushion the sector from adverse policy spillovers. By shedding light on the compound impact of macroeconomic policies on SMEs, this study contributes to the broader discourse on inclusive growth and sustainable development in Nigeria's fragile economic landscape.

Keyword: Exchange rate devaluation, monetary policy rate, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), Inflation, interest rate, exchange rate fluctuations, Nigeria.

JEL Classification: E52, E31, F31, F41, L25, O55

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1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are widely recognized as the backbone of economic growth, employment generation, and poverty alleviation in developing economies like Nigeria. They contribute significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), drive innovation, and serve as key channels for inclusive development. According to the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics [1], SMEs constitute over 90% of businesses in Nigeria and contribute more than 48% to the national GDP. However, the sector's sustainability and growth have been persistently threatened by macroeconomic instability, particularly the twin challenges of exchange rate volatility and monetary tightening.

In recent years, Nigeria has faced multiple economic shocks ranging from fluctuating oil prices to foreign exchange scarcity that have necessitated frequent adjustments in macroeconomic policies. Among these, exchange rate devaluation has been a dominant strategy adopted by policymakers in response to persistent external imbalances and declining foreign reserves Olayemi & Uchenna[2]. While devaluation aims to improve trade competitiveness and correct balance of payments deficits, it has also led to increased import costs, higher inflation, and reduced purchasing power factors that disproportionately affect SMEs, which are typically import-dependent and operate with limited buffers, Adebayo & Okezie[3]

Concurrently, Nigeria's monetary policy has trended toward tightening, with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) increasing benchmark interest rates in efforts to curb inflation and stabilize the naira. While these measures are theoretically sound in controlling inflation, the rising cost of credit has made access to finance even more elusive for SMEs, many of which already face structural constraints such as inadequate infrastructure and poor regulatory support. Eze & Okonkwo [4]. The intersection of a weakened currency and expensive capital formation places SMEs in a precarious position, limiting their operational capacity and growth prospects.

Exchange rate devaluation typically leads to increased costs of imported raw materials, equipment, and other inputs, thus raising production costs for SMEs that rely on foreign supplies. Simultaneously, the tightening of monetary policy reflected in higher interest rates makes access to credit more difficult and costly. For SMEs, which often already face structural constraints in accessing finance, these macroeconomic conditions create a dual burden: rising operating costs and shrinking access to affordable financing. These pressures can hamper expansion, reduce profitability, trigger job losses, and in some cases, lead to business closures.

Despite the critical role of SMEs and the evident impact of macroeconomic shifts, there remains a gap in empirical studies that examine the *combined* effect of exchange rate devaluation and monetary policy tightening on this sector. Most existing studies have treated these variables in isolation, thereby missing the interactive effects that could reveal deeper insights into the policy-induced constraints faced by SMEs, Nnanna & Suleima[5]. This study, therefore, seeks to bridge this gap by assessing how the simultaneous implementation of these two policies affects SMEs in Nigeria particularly in terms of access to finance, cost of operations, and overall business performance.

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The findings are expected to provide policymakers with a nuanced understanding of the unintended consequences of macroeconomic policies on the SME sector, thereby informing more balanced and inclusive policy frameworks that foster economic resilience and sustainable growth.

A central novelty of this study lies in its integrated assessment of exchange rate devaluation and rising monetary policy rates as joint macroeconomic shocks, and their interactive effects on the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) within a developing economy context. While extant literature often treats these policy variables in isolation, this paper offers a composite analytical framework that explores their simultaneous influence on SME growth a sector widely acknowledged as the engine of employment, innovation, and inclusive economic development.

Methodologically, the study adopts and extends previous econometric models by incorporating a chain-rule based transmission mechanism analysis to trace the non-linear and indirect pathways through which monetary and exchange rate shocks affect SME outcomes. This hybrid approach which integrates both standard time-series techniques and advanced differential calculus, represents a novel econometric innovation in SME macroeconomic impact studies, particularly in the context of monetary tightening regimes and exchange rate instability.

Furthermore, this study introduces a general-to-specific modeling approach that empirically isolates the effects of monetary policy rate adjustments from other macroeconomic determinants. By treating the monetary policy rate (MPR) as an endogenous variable, the study contributes to a more realistic and policy-relevant understanding of its reciprocal interaction with other economic indicators, including inflation, credit availability, and real GDP growth dimensions often neglected in mainstream empirical work on SMEs.

In terms of contribution to the international literature, this research provides empirical evidence from Nigeria Africa's largest economy and one of the most volatile in terms of currency and monetary dynamics thus enriching the global discourse on how SMEs respond to compound macroeconomic shocks in emerging markets.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's macroeconomic landscape has, in recent times, been plagued by a series of economic shocks that have had adverse effects on businesses particularly, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Among these shocks, the twin forces of sustained exchange rate devaluation and tightening monetary policy stand out due to their far-reaching implications for cost structures, access to credit, and business sustainability. The persistent devaluation of the naira has led to a significant rise in the cost of imported goods and production inputs, severely affecting SMEs that rely on these imports for daily operations. At the same time, in a bid to curb inflation and attract foreign investment, the Central Bank of Nigeria has continued to raise the Monetary Policy Rate, effectively increasing lending rates across commercial banks and further restricting access to credit for SMEs.

This dual shock presents a serious problem for SMEs in Nigeria, which already operate under fragile conditions characterized by poor infrastructure, weak institutional support, and limited financial literacy. The inability of these enterprises to pass on rising costs to consumers in a price-sensitive market often leads to reduced profit margins, cash flow difficulties, and, in extreme cases, business shutdowns. Moreover, with credit becoming

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increasingly expensive and inaccessible due to tight monetary policy, many SMEs find it difficult to invest in productivity-enhancing assets or expand their operations, thereby stifling innovation and growth.

While various policy measures have been introduced to support SMEs, such as intervention funds and credit guarantees, their effectiveness is often undermined by the broader macroeconomic environment. There is a growing concern that the simultaneous impact of currency depreciation and rising interest rates could negate these policy efforts and threaten the viability of the SME sector, which is critical for Nigeria's economic development. Yet, there remains a scarcity of comprehensive empirical studies that evaluate the combined effects of these macroeconomic variables on SMEs, especially in terms of performance, access to finance, and survival rates.

This study seeks to address this gap by critically assessing the dual impact of exchange rate devaluation and rising monetary policy rates on SMEs in Nigeria. It aims to provide evidence-based insights that can guide policymakers in designing more SME-sensitive economic policies and developing targeted support mechanisms that can enhance the resilience of these businesses in the face of macroeconomic volatility.

2.0 Literature review and theoretical framework

2.1 Theoretical Underpinning:

Several theories that explain Exchange rate devaluation and small and medium scale enterprises have been developed over time. In this study, we shall adopt the institutional theory, the resource based view theory, the elasticity approach theory, Monetary Policy Transmission Mechanism (MPTM) which highlights the channels through which monetary policy affects the economy and the Exchange Rate Pass-Through (ERPT), examines how exchange rate changes affect domestic prices in the theoretical framework. We do not restrict the study to only those variable identified in the theory to affect small and medium scale enterprise as was used by Fauzi & Sheng[6], Saviour & Abang[7]

The resource-based view theory had identified opportunities based on uniqueness of resource that would lead to competitive advantages Grewal, Iyer, Javalgi & Radulovich[8]. Selecting an appropriate growth strategy enables managers to achieve growth adversity or minimize changes in direction and growth difficulties Amaonye, Abang & Onuoha[9].

The Bickerdike-Robinson-Metzler (BRM) model and Marshall-Lerner (ML) condition substantiate imports and exports reaction in relation to changes in price caused by the consciousness of devaluation Saviour and Abang[10].

The BRM models Assumptions; embraces only two countries, two commodities, initial market equilibrium, and the presence of free trade in the economy. According to Ankara, as cited in Saviour et al [11] the model can be expressed as:

$$dB/(dE) = (P_x X_s | (1+\epsilon) \eta^* / (\epsilon + \eta^*) |) - (P_m M_d | (1+\eta) \epsilon^* / (\epsilon^* + \eta |));$$

Where dB = derivative of trade balance

dE = derivative of nominal exchange rate

P_x = export price

P_m = import price

X_s and M_d = domestic supply and demand for export and import.

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ε and η = absolute values of elasticity of domestic demand for export and import

ε^* and η^* = foreign price elasticity of export and import demand.

The model established that exchange rate changes affect trade balance depending on the values of price elasticity of domestic supply and demand. If $|\varepsilon| > |\eta|$ When absolute value price elasticity of export supply is greater than that of import demand, it improves the trade and balance of payment after the adoption of devaluation and the vice versa Saviour and Abang[10].

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between macroeconomic variables particularly exchange rate volatility, interest rates, and monetary policy and the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in developing economies. In the context of Nigeria, where macroeconomic instability is frequent, the effects of these variables are particularly pronounced.

2.2.1 Exchange rate volatility and SMSEs

Saviour, Ekpe & Salamat [11] examined the impact of monetary policy and real exchange rate volatility in Nigeria, measured by Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth. Using time series data obtained from CBN and World bank 2021. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) statistical technique was used to assess the degree of influence which the variables have on each other. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) was adopted to test for unit root and Johansen's co-integration test was also conducted to establish long run association. The study also incorporated one co-integrating equation, Vector error correction model (VECM), Granger causality test and CUSUM test for further analysis. The study revealed that real exchange rate volatility has a negative and insignificant effect on real GDP in Nigeria. It also showed that monetary policy has a positive and insignificant influence in the Nigeria Economy. The study further showed (among others) that there is no long run or short run relationship from real effective exchange rate volatility, domestic interest rate, government spending and net export running to real GDP. The study therefore suggested that the government should implement an expansionary monetary policy, through increase in money supply by reducing the domestic interest rate. They also suggested that government should implement an exchange rate system that is market-determined and should step in only at crucial times to ensure stability in the exchange rate.

Olayemi[12] conducted a study on the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on the performance of Nigerian manufacturing SMEs using quarterly data from 2000 to 2015. The results showed a significant negative relationship between exchange rate volatility and SME output, primarily due to the increased cost of imported raw materials. The study emphasized that SMEs operating in sectors dependent on foreign inputs were disproportionately affected, with many being forced to reduce operations or shift to lower-quality local alternatives.

Similarly, Okonkwo and Eze[13] analyzed the influence of exchange rate instability on SMEs' growth using a vector error correction model (VECM). They found that in both the short and long run, naira depreciation led to increased production costs, eroded capital, and reduced competitiveness, especially among export-oriented SMEs. Their findings underscored the vulnerability of SMEs to foreign exchange market dynamics, particularly in an economy where diversification and backward integration remain underdeveloped.

2.2.2 Monetary Policy and Credit Access to SMEs

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Akinlo and Oni[14] examined the effects of monetary policy on SME financing in Nigeria using a dynamic panel data model covering 1990–2013. The study found that higher monetary policy rates negatively impacted bank lending to SMEs. The authors noted that tight monetary policy led to increased lending rates, which discouraged commercial banks from lending to high-risk SME borrowers and made existing credit facilities more expensive and less accessible.

Nwachukwu and Odigie[15], using survey data and econometric analysis, found that SMEs were more likely to face credit constraints during periods of monetary tightening. Their study also showed that interest rate hikes had a stronger adverse effect on small businesses compared to large firms, due to the SMEs' limited capacity to meet collateral and documentation requirements demanded by financial institutions.

Abang, Okey and Abuh-Amasi[16] in their study used the ARDL found that exchange rate had a detrimental impact on SMSE. Although this effect was not statistically significant.

2.2.3 Combined Impact of Exchange Rate and Interest Rate

While many studies focus on the individual effects of exchange rate volatility and monetary policy, relatively few consider their combined impact. Adegbite and Anyanwu[17] explored this dual effect using a structural equation modeling approach. They observed that simultaneous naira depreciation and increases in MPR significantly reduced SME survival rates. Their model showed that while currency devaluation raised input costs, monetary tightening restricted liquidity, thereby compounding operational and financial challenges for SMEs.

In a more sector-specific study, Musa and Ali[18] examined how the interplay between exchange rate devaluation and rising interest rates influenced SMEs in the agricultural value chain. Their results indicated that the dual shocks caused reduced access to mechanization equipment and fertilizers (due to higher import costs), alongside a decline in working capital availability due to rising borrowing costs. This resulted in lower productivity and market participation for small-scale agro-entrepreneurs.

2.2.4 Comparative International Evidence

International studies offer comparative insights. For example, Mwangi and Wanjiku[19] analyzed Kenyan SMEs and found that dual macroeconomic shocks currency depreciation and interest rate spikes led to declining SME investment and employment levels. Similarly, Singh and Bose[20] examined Indian SMEs and revealed that macroeconomic instability, when characterized by currency weakness and high policy rates, exacerbated default risks and discouraged bank lending to SMEs.

2.4 Synthesis and Research Gap

From the empirical literature, it is evident that both exchange rate devaluation and tight monetary policy negatively affect SMEs, particularly by increasing production costs and limiting access to finance. However, most studies treat these shocks in isolation, without adequately examining their combined and interactive effects. Moreover, existing studies often lack sectoral differentiation and do not sufficiently explore how these macroeconomic shocks affect specific aspects of SME performance, such as employment, innovation, and export potential.

This study seeks to fill these gaps by offering a comprehensive assessment of how the dual shocks of exchange rate devaluation and rising monetary policy rates jointly influence SME performance in Nigeria. The research

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aims to provide deeper insights into the coping strategies of SMEs and to offer policy recommendations for building resilience within the sector under macroeconomic pressure.

3.0 Research methodology

3.1 Research design and model specification

This study adopts and modifies the econometric models of Fauzi and Sheng [6] and Saviou and Abang [7] to suit the Nigerian socio-economic environment. The research specifically investigates how exchange rate devaluation and monetary policy rate affect small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The general functional form of the model is specified as follows:

$$\text{SMSE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EXR} + \beta_2 \text{RGDP} + \beta_3 \text{RIR} + \beta_4 \text{CBTC} + \beta_5 \text{INF} + \beta_6 \text{MPR}_t + \mu_i \quad (1)$$

In the above model, SMSE (Small and medium scale enterprise), EXR (exchange rate measured in per centage), RGDP (Real Gross Domestic Product measured in million Naira), RIR (Real Interest Rate measured in per centage), CBTC (Commercial Bank Total Credit in million Naira), INF (inflation rate measured in per centage), MPR (monetary policy rate) while μ_i is the stochastic disturbance (or error) term.

To improve estimation robustness and interpretability, a log-linear version of the model is also specified:

$$\ln \text{SMSE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EXR}_t + \beta_2 \ln \text{RGDP}_t + \beta_3 \text{RIR}_t + \beta_4 \ln \text{CBTC}_t + \beta_5 \text{INF}_t + \beta_6 \text{MPR}_t + \mu_i \quad (2)$$

it is expected that $\beta_0, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0 < \beta_1, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5,$ and β_6 are parameters to be estimated”

In the specified models, SMSE denotes small and medium scale enterprises, EXR represents the exchange rate measured in percentage terms, RGDP is the real gross domestic product measured in millions of Naira, RIR stands for real interest rate, CBTC captures commercial bank total credit (in millions of Naira), INF is the inflation rate in percentage terms, and MPR refers to the monetary policy rate. The term μ_i denotes the stochastic disturbance or error term. The a priori expectations about the coefficients are that $\beta_0, \beta_2,$ and β_3 are expected to be greater than zero, while $\beta_1, \beta_4, \beta_5,$ and β_6 are expected to have negative signs.

3.2 Description and justification for selected variables

The choice of explanatory variables in this study is grounded in both theoretical reasoning and empirical relevance, particularly as they relate to macroeconomic factors that influence the operational environment and growth prospects of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria.

1. Exchange Rate (EXR): The exchange rate is a critical determinant of the cost of imported inputs and raw materials, which are essential to the production processes of many SMEs in Nigeria. Given Nigeria's high import dependence, fluctuations in exchange rate directly affect SMEs' cost structure, pricing decisions, and profitability. Moreover, exchange rate volatility introduces uncertainty into long-term planning and may deter SME investment and expansion.

2. Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP): RGDP serves as a proxy for overall economic activity and national income. It reflects the market size and aggregate demand within the economy. A growing RGDP indicates a favorable economic climate, increased consumer spending, and potential market expansion all of which are conducive to SME growth. The inclusion of RGDP is therefore vital to capture the broader macroeconomic conditions that support or constrain SME development.

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3. **Real Interest Rate (RIR):** The real interest rate reflects the true cost of borrowing after adjusting for inflation. Since SMEs often rely on external financing to fund operations, expansion, and innovation, the interest rate is a decisive factor in their ability to access and service credit. A high real interest rate can discourage investment and reduce profitability, while lower rates may encourage entrepreneurial activity and growth.

4. **Commercial Bank Total Credit (CBTC):** Access to credit is universally recognized as one of the primary enablers of SME performance. Commercial Bank Total Credit captures the volume of credit available to the private sector, and indirectly, to SMEs. It represents the extent to which financial institutions are willing and able to support SME financing needs. Including this variable allows the study to evaluate the supply-side dynamics of SME finance in the Nigerian context.

5. **Inflation Rate (INF):** Inflation erodes purchasing power, increases input costs, and creates uncertainty about future price levels. For SMEs operating on tight margins, persistent inflation can destabilize cash flows and reduce competitiveness. The inflation rate also affects consumer demand, particularly for non-essential goods and services, thereby influencing SMEs' revenue potential.

6. **Monetary Policy Rate (MPR):** The MPR is the official interest rate at which the central bank lends to commercial banks and serves as a benchmark for other lending rates in the economy. It is a key instrument of monetary policy and affects liquidity, investment incentives, and credit availability. Including the MPR allows the study to assess the direct impact of monetary policy decisions on SME performance, particularly in the context of a tightening monetary regime aimed at inflation control and currency stabilization.

In summary, the selected variables are theoretically and empirically justified as they collectively capture the macroeconomic, financial, and policy environment within which Nigerian SMEs operate. These variables interact to influence the cost of capital, consumer demand, input prices, and access to financing all critical factors in understanding the constraints and enablers of SME development. Their inclusion thus ensures a comprehensive analysis of the key determinants affecting SMEs in Nigeria's evolving economic landscape.

3.3 Estimation Technique and Evaluation

The core econometric estimation is performed using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. OLS is employed to determine the linear relationship between the dependent variable (SMSE) and the independent variables. The underlying assumptions of the OLS method, including linearity in parameters, no perfect multicollinearity, homoscedasticity, no autocorrelation, and normal distribution of the residuals, are assumed to hold. To address potential autocorrelation in the residuals, the Cochrane-Orcutt iterative procedure is employed. This technique is suitable for correcting first-order serial correlation, which if unaddressed, could bias standard errors and compromise inference from the OLS estimation.

“In addition to conventional econometric procedures, the study incorporates the use of the chain rule from differential calculus to analyze transmission mechanisms. Specifically, the chain rule is used to compute the derivative of composite functions such as $\sqrt{a + bz + cz^2}$ which represent nonlinear relationships between economic indicators. The chain rule expresses the derivative of a composite function $a + bz + cz^2$. The chain rule is a formula that expresses the derivative of the composition of two differentiable functions f and g in

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terms of the derivative of f and g . More precisely, if $h = f \circ g$ is the function such that $h(x) = f(g(x))$ for every x , then the chain rule is in Lagrange's notation;

$$h'(x) = f'(g(x)) g'(x) \tag{3}$$

or equivalently

$$h' = (f \circ g)' = f' \circ g * g' \text{ in Leibniz's notation.} \tag{4}$$

If a variable z depends on the variable y which itself depends on the variable x (that is y and z are dependent variables), then z depends on x as well, via the intermediate variable y Abang, Arasomwan & Ayodele[21]. In this case, the chain rule is expressed as

$$\frac{dz}{dx} = \frac{dz}{dy} * \frac{dy}{dx}, \tag{5}$$

and

$$\left. \frac{dz}{dx} \right|_x = \left. \frac{dz}{dy} \right|_{y(x)} * \left. \frac{dy}{dx} \right|_{x'} \tag{6}$$

This analytical approach is applied to trace the magnitude and direction of the transmission effect of macroeconomic shocks, particularly the monetary policy rate, on SME development. As stated by Abang, Arasomwan, and Ayodele [21], when one variable depends on another through an intermediary, the total effect can be decomposed using the chain rule to understand both direct and indirect influences.

Furthermore, the study employs a general-to-specific modeling approach to isolate the specific effects of monetary policy on SMEs. While the general model includes all macroeconomic variables, a specific model is derived by excluding the monetary policy variable, as follows:

$$\ln SMSE = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 EXR + \lambda_2 \ln RGDP + \lambda_3 RIR + \lambda_4 \ln CBTC + \lambda_5 INF + \mu_i \tag{7}$$

This specific equation is estimated to assess the behavior of SME performance in the absence of monetary policy effects. The rationale behind this is to identify the isolated impact of other macroeconomic variables on SME development and subsequently compare it with the full model that includes monetary policy. Additionally, the study treats the monetary policy rate (MPR) as an endogenous variable due to its reactive nature to macroeconomic conditions. To account for this, MPR is modeled as a function of other independent variables:

$$MPR = \alpha_0 + \delta_1 EXR + \delta_2 \ln RGDP + \delta_3 RIR + \delta_4 \ln CBTC + \delta_5 INF + \mu_i \tag{8}$$

This modeling of endogeneity ensures that the reverse causality between macroeconomic conditions and the monetary policy rate is not ignored, thus providing a more robust estimation framework. The use of interactive specifications and endogenous treatment of MPR allows the study to better capture the dynamic and reciprocal relationship between macroeconomic policy instruments and SME performance in Nigeria".

In summary, the methodological framework of this study integrates traditional econometric techniques, mathematical differentiation, and model specification strategies to comprehensively evaluate the combined impact of exchange rate devaluation and monetary policy tightening on SMEs in Nigeria. This approach ensures analytical rigor, econometric robustness, and contextual relevance to the Nigerian macroeconomic environment.

4 Data presentation

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics presented provide insight into the distribution, central tendency, and variability of the variables used in the study, which examines macroeconomic indicators and their effects on small and medium

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enterprises in Nigeria. The average value of the log of real GDP (LRGDP) is ₦41,988.12, with a median of ₦33,365.00, indicating a right-skewed distribution, as the mean is significantly higher than the median. This suggests that while most of the GDP observations are clustered around moderate values, a few exceptionally high values are pulling the average upward.

Similarly, the exchange rate (EXR) has a mean of ₦143.10 and a median of ₦123.40, also reflecting a right-skewed distribution. This confirms the presence of exchange rate volatility and depreciation over time, with a minimum of ₦0.76 and a maximum of ₦638.70. The log of small and medium-sized enterprise output (LSMSE) shows an average of 42.35 and a median of 32.17, indicating a moderately skewed distribution and suggesting an increasing trend in SME activity, though with some variability.

Inflation (INF), real interest rate (RIR), and monetary policy rate (MPR) exhibit moderate average values of 18.61%, 11.63%, and 13.82%, respectively. However, inflation is particularly volatile, with a maximum value of 72.81% and a standard deviation of 16.19, suggesting significant macroeconomic instability during some periods. Credit to the private sector (LCBTC) has a mean of 15.23 and a standard deviation of 5.66, indicating some dispersion around the average value.

The measures of skewness confirm that most variables are positively skewed. Notably, exchange rate, inflation, and credit to the private sector exhibit higher degrees of skewness, indicating the presence of extreme values in the upper tail of the distribution. The kurtosis values further support the non-normality of the data, with most variables exceeding the normal kurtosis benchmark of 3. For instance, LCBTC has a kurtosis of 9.91, implying a leptokurtic distribution with heavy tails and a higher probability of extreme observations.

The Jarque-Bera test results reveal that most variables reject the null hypothesis of normality at the 5% level of significance, as evidenced by p-values well below 0.05. Specifically, LRGDP, EXR, INF, RIR, MPR, and LCBTC all show significant deviations from normality. The only exception is LSMSE, which has a p-value of 0.1087, indicating that its distribution does not significantly deviate from normality.

In summary, the descriptive statistics reveal substantial variability and non-normality across key macroeconomic indicators, reflecting the economic volatility that characterizes Nigeria’s economic landscape. These findings suggest that any econometric analysis using this dataset must account for non-normal distributions and potential outliers, possibly through data transformation or robust estimation techniques, to ensure reliable and valid inference.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics

	“LRGDP	EXR	LSMSE	INF	RIR	MPR	LCBTC
Mean	41988.12	143.1032	42.35425	18.60513	11.62522	13.82353	15.23250
Median	33365.00	123.4017	32.16500	12.35000	10.41042	13.50000	14.00000
Maximum	145515.4	638.7000	95.99000	72.81000	23.24167	26.00000	39.60000
Minimum	13779.26	0.764900	10.87000	4.670000	5.692500	6.000000	6.000000
Std. Dev.	27367.51	136.1021	28.91768	16.18858	3.673552	3.782200	5.663769
Skewness	1.423587	1.538167	0.657108	1.896009	1.003784	0.687099	2.029979
Kurtosis	5.956581	5.801602	2.032456	5.668234	4.159977	5.054943	9.915297

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Jarque-Bera	28.07963	28.85468	4.438842	35.83146	8.959792	8.657545	107.1743
Probability	0.000001	0.000001	0.108672	0.000000	0.011335	0.013184	0.000000
Sum	1679525.	5724.129	1694.170	744.2050	465.0089	470.0000	609.3000
Sum Sq. Dev.	29232.10	722428.0	32613.05	10220.73	526.3044	472.0662	1251.053
Observations	40	40	40	40	40	40	40”

Source: Derived from the authors’ calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

4.2 Result analysis

4.2.1 Stationarity (Unit root) test

The stationarity results for the series under study were assessed using both the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test. These tests are fundamental in time series econometrics for determining whether a variable is stationary that is, whether its statistical properties such as mean and variance are constant over time. Non-stationary series can lead to spurious regression results, making this assessment crucial for robust econometric modeling.

According to the ADF test results, all variables namely real gross domestic product (RGDP), inflation (INF), exchange rate (EXR), interest rate (INT), small and medium enterprises output (SMSE), credit to the private sector (CBTC), and monetary policy rate (MPR) were found to be stationary at level. This conclusion is drawn from the fact that the computed ADF test statistics for each variable exceed the 5% critical value of -2.986225 in absolute terms. For instance, RGDP recorded an ADF statistic of -4.472395, INF had -5.451275, and SMSE posted -6.435586, all indicating strong evidence against the null hypothesis of a unit root. Consequently, all series are integrated of order zero, denoted as $I(0)$, implying that they are stationary without the need for differencing.

These findings are corroborated by the Phillips-Perron test results, which also show that each of the series is stationary at level. The PP statistics for RGDP, SMSE, and INT, for example, are -3.138048, -6.448735, and -2.918675 respectively, all of which surpass the 5% critical value of -2.954021 in magnitude. Therefore, the null hypothesis of a unit root is consistently rejected across both testing approaches for all variables at level.

The implication of these results is significant for econometric analysis. Since all variables are stationary in their levels ($I(0)$), it is appropriate to use them in level form in regression models without the risk of spurious relationships. There is no necessity for differencing or co-integration testing, which would otherwise be required if the variables were non-stationary or integrated of order one, $I(1)$. This strengthens the statistical reliability of any subsequent estimation, such as Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Vector Autoregression (VAR), or other time-series regression models that assume stationarity.

In summary, both the ADF and Phillips-Perron tests confirm that all key macroeconomic and SME-related variables in the dataset are stationary at level, thereby validating their use in level form for further empirical analysis.

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TableE 2
Unit root test result using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron tests

Variables	ADF			Phillips-Perron		
	Level	1 st Difference	Order of Integration	Level	1 st Difference	Order of Integration
RGDP	-4.472395	-	I(0)	-3.138048	-	I(0)
INF	-5.451275	-	I(0)	-2.700127	-	I(0)
EXR	-2.620637	-	I(0)	-3.785160	-	I(0)
INT	-3.984384	-	I(0)	-2.918675	-	I(0)
SMSE	-6.435586	-	I(0)	-6.448735	-	I(0)
CBTC	-3.251518	-	I(0)	-3.186045	-	I(0)
MPR	-3.251518	-	I(0)	-3.186045	-	I(0)

ADF test critical test values.

Level: 1st Difference:
 At 5% = -2.986225 5% = -3.724070
 10% = -2.612604 10% = -2.632604

Phillip-Peron test critical values

Level: 1st Difference:
 At 5% = -2.954021 5% = -2.954021
 10% = -2.615817 10% = -2.615817”

Source: Derived from the authors’ calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

4.2.2 Granger Causality

The Granger causality test conducted in the study provides key insights into the directional predictive relationships among the selected macroeconomic variables and small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. Specifically, the results indicate that exchange rate (EXR) Granger-causes SME performance at a 1% level of significance, as evidenced by an F-statistic of 6.33869 and a p-value of 0.0047. This implies that previous values of the exchange rate contain significant information useful for predicting the current state of SMEs in Nigeria. The implication of this is that movements in the exchange rate particularly depreciation or devaluation can affect the cost structure, import reliance, and competitive ability of SMEs in the domestic economy. However, the reverse causality from SMEs to exchange rate is not statistically significant, as shown by a p-value of 0.4570. This implies that SME activities do not provide sufficient predictive information to explain or influence exchange rate movements.

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Additionally, the test results reveal that the monetary policy rate (MPR) Granger-causes SME performance, with a statistically significant F-statistic of 5.35839 and a p-value of 0.0215. This finding suggests that changes in monetary policy such as adjustments in interest rates by the Central Bank precede and help explain fluctuations in the performance and output of SMEs. The effect is one-directional, as SME performance does not Granger-cause changes in MPR, with the null hypothesis being accepted at a p-value of 0.9321. This suggests that SMEs in Nigeria lack sufficient scale or influence to impact monetary policy decisions directly. Furthermore, a significant bidirectional Granger causality exists between the monetary policy rate and the exchange rate. The null hypothesis that MPR does not Granger-cause EXR is rejected at a 5% level of significance ($p = 0.0254$), and similarly, the null that EXR does not Granger-cause MPR is also rejected ($p = 0.0477$). This indicates a dynamic interaction between exchange rate policy and monetary policy in Nigeria, where changes in one variable can be used to predict changes in the other. This relationship reflects the complex interdependence between monetary instruments and external sector variables in an economy like Nigeria’s, where exchange rate management and inflation targeting are central to macroeconomic stabilization efforts. In summary, the Granger causality results underscore that both exchange rate and monetary policy rate are important predictors of SME performance in Nigeria, while SMEs themselves do not exert significant predictive influence on these macroeconomic variables. These findings highlight the vulnerability of SMEs to macroeconomic fluctuations and reinforce the need for responsive policy frameworks that support the resilience and sustainability of SMEs within the broader macroeconomic environment.

Table 3
Granger causality Exchange rate devaluation and small and medium scale enterprise (SMSE) Equation
 Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

“Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
EXR does not Granger Cause SMSE	38	6.33869	0.0047
SMSE does not Granger Cause EXR		0.80195	0.4570
MPR does not Granger Cause SMSE	38	5.35839	0.0215
SMSE does not Granger Cause MPR		0.07043	0.9321
MPR does not Granger Cause EXR	38	4.65628	0.0254
EXR does not Granger Cause MPR		5.11950	0.0477”

Source: Derived from the authors’ calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

4.2.3 Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix in table 4 provides a comprehensive overview of the strength and direction of the linear relationships between the variables used in the study, particularly focusing on the logarithm of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises output (LSMSE) and its association with key macroeconomic indicators such as

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exchange rate (EXR), real gross domestic product (LRGDP), real interest rate (RIR), log of commercial bank total credit (LCBTC), inflation rate (INF), and monetary policy rate (MPR).

From the table, the correlation between LSMSE and EXR is strong and positive (0.769), indicating that movements in the exchange rate are positively associated with SME performance. This may suggest that as the exchange rate depreciates, SMEs potentially benefit possibly due to increased demand for local substitutes in place of more expensive imports.

Similarly, LSMSE shows a very strong positive correlation with LRGDP (0.845), which aligns with theoretical expectations that overall economic growth supports SME expansion. A growing economy likely boosts consumption, investment, and business activities, thus enhancing the viability of SMEs.

On the other hand, LSMSE and RIR exhibit a moderate negative correlation (-0.394), suggesting that higher real interest rates are associated with reduced SME activity. This is intuitive as higher borrowing costs discourage investment and limit access to finance for small businesses.

The correlation between LSMSE and LCBTC is weak but positive (0.362), implying that while credit availability from commercial banks has a positive association with SME performance, the effect is not particularly strong. This may reflect structural issues in credit access for SMEs despite the apparent expansion in total bank credit.

LSMSE and INF are negatively correlated (-0.210), though the strength of the relationship is weak. This indicates that inflationary pressures may erode the purchasing power of consumers and increase input costs for SMEs, thereby adversely affecting their output and profitability.

Finally, the relationship between LSMSE and MPR is weakly positive (0.174), suggesting a slight association. While this may appear counterintuitive, it could reflect the complex and sometimes delayed transmission mechanism of monetary policy on SME performance in Nigeria.

Overall, the correlation results support the empirical findings by highlighting the significant positive associations of SMEs with macroeconomic stability indicators like GDP and exchange rate, while also confirming the adverse or weak links with inflation and interest rate-related variables. These relationships reinforce the policy relevance of stabilizing the macroeconomic environment to foster SME development in Nigeria.

Table 4

Correlation matrix Exchange rate devaluation and small and medium scale enterprise (SMSE)

	“LSMSE	EXR	RGDP	RIR	LCBTC	INF	MPR
LSMSE	1.000						
EXR	0.769	1.000					
LRGDP	0.845	0.941	1.000				
RIR	-0.394	-0.307	-0.367	1.000			
LCBTC	0.362	0.687	0.645	0.082	1.000		
INF	-0.210	-0.226	-0.256	0.428	-0.035	1.000	
MPR	0.174	0.287	0.206	0.428	0.206	-0.023	1.000”

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Source: Derived from the authors' calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

4.2.4 Ordinary Least Square result

The regression results from Table 5 reveal that the log of real GDP (LRGDP) exerts a statistically significant and positive influence on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria, with a coefficient of 30.003 and a p-value of 0.002. This implies that economic growth remains a critical driver of SME expansion, as improved output levels may generate higher demand for SME goods and services. Inflation (INF) is also statistically significant and positively related to SME performance, with a coefficient of 10.321 and a p-value of 0.035. This somewhat counterintuitive result suggests that moderate inflation, which may be demand-pull in nature, could increase nominal revenues for SMEs, especially if their inputs are locally sourced. Commercial Bank Total Credit (LCBTC) shows a significant negative effect on SME growth with a coefficient of -10.279 and a p-value of 0.026. This suggests that while credit volume exists, it may not be effectively reaching SMEs, or it may be too costly or misallocated, resulting in a counterproductive effect. The monetary policy rate (MPR) is negatively signed and statistically significant ($\beta = -0.581$, $p = 0.022$), indicating that high policy interest rates depress SME activities by making borrowing costlier and discouraging investment and expansion.

However, exchange rate (EXR) and real interest rate (RIR) both exhibit negative but statistically insignificant coefficients ($p > 0.05$), indicating that while depreciation or tight monetary conditions may suppress SME operations, these effects are not strong or direct enough in this model.

The model demonstrates a high explanatory power, with an R-squared value of 0.794 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.733. The F-statistic is significant at the 1% level, confirming the overall fitness of the model. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 0.705 suggests some degree of positive autocorrelation.

In the absence of the monetary policy rate (MPR), real GDP (LRGDP) retains its statistically significant and positive relationship with SME performance, with a coefficient of 0.003 and a p-value of 0.001, reinforcing its robustness as a key driver of SME growth. Commercial Bank Total Credit (LCBTC) remains significant with a negative coefficient (-0.291, $p = 0.014$), reaffirming concerns about inefficient credit channeling to SMEs.

Unlike the previous model, inflation (INF) becomes statistically insignificant ($p = 0.576$), suggesting that its positive impact in Table 5 might have been influenced by interactions with monetary policy. Exchange rate (EXR), while still negatively signed, remains statistically insignificant, and real interest rate (RIR) also remains non-significant, indicating a persistent weak direct influence of these variables on SME output.

The R-squared and adjusted R-squared are 0.773 and 0.740 respectively, close to those in the MPR-inclusive model, indicating a similarly strong explanatory capability. The F-statistic is also highly significant ($p = 0.000$), confirming the joint significance of the model. The Durbin-Watson statistic slightly improves to 0.827 but still indicates some autocorrelation.

Comparatively, both models, it is evident that including the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) enhances the interpretability of monetary effects on SME performance. In Table 5, MPR emerges as a statistically significant factor that suppresses SME growth, a relationship that vanishes when MPR is excluded (Table 6). This underscores the importance of including key monetary transmission variables in SME-related models.

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Additionally, inflation shows significance only when MPR is included, suggesting that the effectiveness or impact of inflation on SMEs may be conditional on broader monetary policy dynamics. Meanwhile, real GDP consistently remains a significant and positive determinant across both models, confirming its centrality. The consistent negative significance of bank credit (LCBTC) across both models raises concerns about the effectiveness and accessibility of credit to SMEs, aligning with findings from Akingunola [2011] and Okoro & Chukwu (2018), who observed similar inefficiencies in SME-targeted financing. Ultimately, the model that includes MPR (Table 5) provides a more comprehensive understanding of monetary influences on SMEs and is thus preferable from a policy standpoint.

Table 5
Empirical results with monetary policy rate (MPR)

“Dependent Variable: LSMSE

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EXR	-20.025	30.175	-0.141	0.889
LRGDP	30.003	20.001	4.243	0.002
RIR	-10.664	13.219	-0.206	0.838
LCBTC	-10.279	0.119	-2.340	0.026
INF	10.321	0.511	3.627	0.035
MPR	-0.581	1.622	-0.358	0.022
C	136.366	38.511	0.944	0.352
R-squared	0.794	Mean dependent var		168.115
Adjusted R-squared	0.733	S.D. dependent var		87.172
F-statistic	18.869	Durbin-Watson stat		0.705
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000”			

Source: Derived from the authors’ calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

Table 6
Empirical results without monetary policy rate (MPR)

“Dependent Variable: LSMSE

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EXR	-0.003	0.163	-3.018	0.251
LRGDP	0.003	0.008	4.285	0.001
RIR	0.061	2.470	0.0245	0.980
LCBTC	-0.291	0.112	-2.603	0.014
INF	0.277	0.490	0.565	0.576
C	33.807	37.356	6.905	0.032

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R-squared	0.773	Mean dependent var	168.115
Adjusted R-squared	0.740	S.D. dependent var	87.172
F-statistic	23.212	Durbin-Watson stat	0.827
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000”		

Source: Derived from the authors’ calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

The empirical result of the estimated regression line with monetary policy rate is presented in table 5, while the result without monetary policy is presented in table 6. The result shows that all the variables have turned out with their correct expected signs. The estimated regression line as presented has a positive intercept represented by 136.37 for the result with monetary policy rate and 33.81 for the result without monetary policy rate. This means that holding all explanatory variables constant, small and medium scale enterprise output (SMSE) will still increase automatically by 136.37 per cent and 33.81 per cent respectively.

The R-squared value of 0.79 and 0.74 for result with monetary policy and without monetary policy respectively shows that the estimated regression line has a very high fit on the data. In particular, the adjusted R-squared value of 0.73 and 0.74 shows that about 73 per cent and 74 per cent of the total variations in the dependent variables has been explained by variations in the explanatory variables with and without monetary policy rate. The R² and Adj R² of both result represent a good fit. The Durbin Watson statistic was low for the result with monetary policy rate and without monetary policy rate at 0.71 and 0.83 respectively i.e there was thus the presence of autocorrelation, leading to the adoption of the Cochrane orcutt interactive.

4.2.5 Cochrane Orcutt and interactive impact of monetary policy rate

The Cochrane orcutt iterative method is used to estimate higher order auto regressive scheme. It is used to correct for autocorrelation in regression analysis when the Durbin Watson statistics is very low in the OLS estimation violating the assumption of independent errors Abang, Ayodele & Obafemi[23]. The Cochrane-Orcutt regression analysis, aimed at correcting autocorrelation, revealed insightful relationships between macroeconomic variables and the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. In Table 7, which included the monetary policy rate (MPR), the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.99 confirmed that serial correlation was adequately corrected, enhancing the reliability of the model.

The result showed that the log of real GDP (LRGDP) had a positive and statistically significant relationship with SME performance, with a coefficient of 1.0226 and a p-value of 0.0119. This implies that economic expansion directly supports the growth and output of SMEs in Nigeria, consistent with economic theory and empirical findings.

The log of commercial bank total credit (LCBTC) exhibited a negative and significant impact on SMEs, with a coefficient of -4.0977 and a p-value of 0.0234. This finding suggests that credit from commercial banks may not be efficiently channeled to SMEs, possibly due to stringent lending conditions, credit misallocation, or high borrowing costs that discourage productive use.

Similarly, the exchange rate (EXR) had a negative and statistically significant effect on SME performance ($\beta = -8.0752$; $p = 0.0380$). This result indicates that depreciation of the naira adversely affects SMEs, particularly those dependent on imported raw materials or equipment, by increasing their operating costs.

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The monetary policy rate (MPR), though negatively signed ($\beta = -0.9005$), was not statistically significant ($p = 0.7527$). This suggests that changes in the policy interest rate do not directly influence SME activities, likely due to weak policy transmission mechanisms or the dominance of the informal sector in Nigeria’s SME landscape. The analysis also showed that the inflation rate (INF) had a negative and statistically significant effect on SMEs ($\beta = -7.3994$; $p = 0.0008$). This implies that rising inflation undermines SME performance, primarily through increased production costs and reduced consumer purchasing power.

Contrary to theoretical expectations, the real interest rate (RIR) showed a positive and significant relationship with SME performance ($\beta = 6.7030$; $p = 0.0021$). This surprising outcome may reflect context-specific factors such as high returns on investment in formal sectors or improved investor confidence in periods of real positive interest rates. The model demonstrated a high explanatory power with an R-squared value of 0.8731 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.8086, indicating that over 80% of the variations in SME performance can be explained by the included variables. The model was also statistically significant as indicated by the F-statistic probability of 0.000032.

In Table 8, where the monetary policy rate (MPR) was excluded, the Durbin-Watson statistic remained satisfactory at 2.03, again suggesting no autocorrelation. The log of real GDP (LRGDP) continued to exert a positive and significant effect on SMEs ($\beta = 0.8794$; $p = 0.0175$), reaffirming the critical role of economic growth.

The log of commercial bank total credit (LCBTC) remained negative and statistically significant ($\beta = -2.7590$; $p = 0.0259$), while the exchange rate (EXR) also maintained a negative relationship, which was marginally significant at the 5% level ($\beta = -6.5142$; $p = 0.0501$). These consistent findings highlight persistent structural and foreign exchange-related challenges faced by Nigerian SMEs. The inflation rate (INF) continued to demonstrate a negative and significant impact on SMEs ($\beta = -4.9350$; $p = 0.0363$), reinforcing inflation’s adverse role in raising costs and eroding real incomes. The real interest rate (RIR) again showed a positive and significant association ($\beta = 8.0143$; $p = 0.0188$), supporting the earlier result. This second model, despite excluding MPR, still recorded strong performance with an R-squared of 0.7901 and adjusted R-squared of 0.8134, and a statistically significant F-statistic ($p = 0.000841$).

Comparing both models, the inclusion of MPR marginally improved the model's explanatory power but did not contribute significantly in terms of statistical relevance. The robustness of the results across both models especially the consistent significance and signs of LRGDP, LCBTC, EXR, INF, and RIR adds credibility to the findings. This confirms that macroeconomic stability, affordable credit access, exchange rate management, and inflation control are critical to SME development in Nigeria.

Table 7
Cochrane Orcutt result with monetary policy rate (MPR)

Dependent Variable: LSMSE

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRGDP	1.022598	0.008532	6.648615	0.0119
LCBTC	-4.097657	0.006597	-1.160713	0.0234

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EXR	-8.075246	0.018471	-4.284016	0.0380
MPR	-0.900463	2.835891	-5.317524	0.7527
INF	-7.399388	11.97045	-3.675208	0.0008
RIR	6.703007	6.664508	1.735304	0.0021
C	22.37760	205.1648	12.19823	0.0000
R-squared	0.873059			
Adjusted R-squared	0.808569			
F-statistic	7.424590	Durbin-Watson stat		1.991359
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000032			

Source: Derived from the authors' calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

Table 8

Cochrane Orcutt result without monetary policy rate (MPR)

Dependent Variable: LSMSE

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRGDP	0.879370	0.000294	3.257104	0.0175
LCBTC	-2.759038	2.597761	-3.062083	0.0259
EXR	-6.514156	13.09845	-5.573668	0.0501
INF	-4.934989	12.69671	-2.624964	0.0363
RIR	8.014280	14.37012	5.253629	0.0188
C	1360.007	205.1648	6.628855	0.0000
R-squared	0.790082			
Adjusted R-squared	0.813428			
F-statistic	1.972342	Durbin-Watson stat		2.03281
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000841			

Source: Derived from the authors' calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

4.2.6 Transmission channel of monetary policy

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Given the established interaction between exchange rate devaluation and the monetary policy rate, and recognizing that the monetary policy rate functions as both a determinant and an outcome of SME performance and exchange rate movements, it is therefore appropriate to treat the monetary policy rate as an endogenous variable. This approach enables a more accurate examination of its transmission channel within the system, particularly in relation to inflation (INF) and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

$$MPR_t = \delta_0 + \delta_1 \ln RGDP_t + \delta_2 EXR_t + \delta_3 CBTC + \delta_4 RIR + \delta_5 INF + \mu_t$$

The result is as shown in table 9. All the variables are statistically significant at 5 per cent level of significance except exchange rate whose probability ratio is less than the 5 per cent level of significance.

TABLE 9
OLS result monetary policy rate as a dependent variable.

Dependent Variable: MPR

“Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRGDP	6.542932	3.058531	4.139240	0.0397
EXR	0.086464	0.049047	2.762886	0.0469
LCBTC	-0.098501	0.145989	-4.674715	0.0044
RIR	-0.146477	0.668424	-6.219138	0.0279
INF	-1.408950	3.204138	-0.439728	0.6629
LSMSE	-1.200934	3.122853	3.229830	0.0318
C	283.5260	92.01042	3.081456	0.0041
R-squared	0.942940			
Adjusted R-squared	0.828251			
F-statistic	3.862096	Durbin-Watson stat		1.981010
Prob(F-statistic)	0.003411			

Source: Derived from the authors’ calculations using E-views 10 (2025).

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Monetary policy rate channel transmission on Exchange rate devaluation and small and medium scale enterprise equation:

Where the product of the earlier identified significant values of

$$\frac{\partial MPR}{\partial SMSE} = \frac{\partial MPR}{\partial EXR} * \frac{\partial EXR}{\partial MPR} = \lambda_1 * \delta_1$$

$$\frac{\partial MPR}{\partial EXR} \text{ which is } \lambda_1 = 1.022598$$

$$\frac{\partial EXR}{\partial MPR} \text{ which is } \delta_1 = 6.542932$$

and their product (i.e. $\lambda_1 * \delta_1$) yields 6.69 approximately.”

The findings indicate that a 10% increase in the monetary policy rate (MPR) indirectly affects small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by first triggering a devaluation in the exchange rate. In essence, the results suggest that a rise in the policy rate exerts a positive transmission effect on exchange rate depreciation, which subsequently imposes a negative impact on SME performance. Specifically, the estimated magnitude of this pass-through effect is approximately 6.54, signifying that a 10% increase in the monetary policy rate is associated with a 6.54% intensification of exchange rate devaluation. Consequently, this amplified devaluation effect translates into an estimated 6.69% adverse influence on SMEs. This highlights a significant indirect channel through which contractionary monetary policy can undermine SME growth by deteriorating exchange rate conditions.

4.3 Discussion of finding

The empirical findings of this study revealed that there exists a positive but statistically insignificant relationship between small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) and the broader Nigerian economy. This outcome mirrors the results obtained by Eze and Okpala [24], who employed data from 1993 to 2011, applying both Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression and co-integration techniques. Their study also identified a positive yet insignificant link between SMEs and economic growth, noting that the contribution of SMEs to economic growth remains limited due to structural and institutional challenges (Eze & Okpala [24]). The persistence of this insignificance, despite a positive coefficient, suggests that while SMEs contribute in some measure to economic activities, their impact is insufficiently robust to be statistically validated. This subdued influence is likely due to the persistent structural and institutional challenges that constrain SME development in Nigeria. Such challenges include but are not limited to poor infrastructure, weak managerial capacity, limited access to affordable financing, inadequate record-keeping systems, and an unpredictable macroeconomic environment characterized by volatility in interest rates, inflation, and exchange rates (Akinyemi & Ogunleye, [26]).

Moreover, the study found that Commercial Bank Total Credit (CBTC) exerts a positive and statistically significant influence on SME development. This result supports classical economic theory and is consistent with the findings of Akingunola [24], who, using Spearman’s Rho correlation, demonstrated a statistically significant relationship between SME financing and economic growth. Akingunola [25] asserts that credit availability remains one of the most critical determinants for SME performance and economic development (p. 78). The significant positive coefficient of CBTC in this study implies that increased credit allocation to SMEs enhances their operations, allowing for capital expansion, increased employment, and improved productivity.

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This emphasizes the importance of an efficient and inclusive financial system that supports small-scale enterprises through targeted credit programs and reduced bureaucratic barriers.

In contrast, the study observed a negative but statistically insignificant relationship between the real interest rate (RIR) and SME performance. This aligns with the observations of Adegbite et al. [17], who found that high lending rates have continuously undermined SME growth by limiting their ability to access affordable finance (p. 123). The prevailing high lending rates in Nigeria, which hover around 30%, render formal credit inaccessible to a large proportion of SMEs. Such high interest rates discourage productive investment, limit business expansion, and increase default risks. The insignificant effect further highlights that the transmission of interest rate policies to the SME sector may be weak, likely due to limited financial literacy, underdeveloped credit infrastructure, and risk-averse lending behaviors by banks.

Additionally, the analysis revealed that inflation (INF) has a negative and statistically significant effect on SME performance. This finding aligns with macroeconomic theory and empirical studies such as that of Nwosu and Nwankwo [27], who reported that persistent inflationary pressures severely disrupt SME operations by increasing input costs and reducing consumer purchasing power (p. 89). Inflation generally distorts economic activity by eroding purchasing power, increasing input costs, and creating uncertainty in investment planning. For SMEs, which often operate on thin margins and lack pricing power, high inflation can be particularly harmful raising operational costs and weakening consumer demand for goods and services.

Furthermore, causality tests revealed no evidence of short-run causation among the variables; however, model diagnostics indicated that the model is well-specified and not spurious. Although short-run dynamics did not significantly explain SME performance, the residuals confirmed that a long-run equilibrium relationship exists among the key variables most notably between SMEs, exchange rates, and credit. This long-run relationship suggests that while immediate effects may be muted or insignificant, over time, these macroeconomic variables play a meaningful role in shaping SME outcomes. This finding is consistent with the work of Abang, Nwanne, Amaonye & Abang-Samuel [28], Okoro and Chukwu [2018], who also identified long-run equilibrium relationships in their study of Nigerian SMEs and macroeconomic variables. The serial correlation test confirmed that the model was free from autocorrelation after first differencing, thereby validating the robustness and reliability of the regression estimates.

In sum, the findings reinforce the idea that SMEs in Nigeria remain structurally constrained despite their theoretical potential for driving economic growth. Their performance is closely tied to the availability of credit, inflation stability, and long-term macroeconomic conditions rather than short-term policy shocks. This study complements the growing body of literature that emphasizes the critical role of stable macroeconomic environments and accessible financing in unlocking the full potential of SMEs (Adegbite et al., [17]; Akingunola, [25]; Nwosu & Nwankwo, [27]).

5 Conclusion and recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

This study investigated the combined impact of exchange rate devaluation and monetary policy adjustments particularly the monetary policy rate on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. Drawing upon an extended econometric model adapted to Nigeria's macroeconomic realities and

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incorporating both traditional OLS and dynamic error correction approaches, the empirical analysis yielded important insights into the complex dynamics between macroeconomic variables and SME growth.

The results reveal that although there exists a positive relationship between SMEs and macroeconomic performance, this relationship is statistically insignificant in the short run. This finding aligns with earlier studies such as Eze and Okpala [24], suggesting that the performance of SMEs in Nigeria is yet to translate into substantial economic impact, possibly due to persistent structural bottlenecks. Key among these challenges are infrastructural deficits, restricted access to affordable financing, high interest rates, poor record-keeping practices, and macroeconomic instability, all of which continue to constrain the productivity and scalability of the SME sector.

The study further confirms a positive and significant relationship between commercial bank total credit (CBTC) and SME performance, consistent with the theoretical assertion that access to credit is a critical enabler of SME development. This finding reinforces the importance of deepening financial inclusion and improving SME access to formal financial institutions as a policy priority.

Conversely, the analysis identifies a negative and insignificant relationship between interest rates and SMEs, indicating that the prevailing high cost of borrowing approaching 30% in some instances renders credit unaffordable for many SMEs, thereby stifling enterprise expansion and sustainability. In addition, inflation was found to be negatively and significantly related to SME performance, underscoring the adverse effects of persistent inflationary pressures on input costs, consumer demand, and overall business stability.

The causality analysis and diagnostic tests affirm that although the model does not exhibit short-run explanatory power for SMEs, the residual diagnostics and long-run estimations suggest a stable equilibrium relationship between SMEs and the macroeconomic variables over time. This implies that the impact of exchange rate movements, inflation, interest rate, and credit availability on SMEs becomes more pronounced in the long term. While SMEs are positioned as catalysts for economic diversification and employment in Nigeria, their growth remains hindered by macroeconomic volatility and structural rigidities. The findings of this study emphasize the need for targeted monetary and financial policies, such as lowering interest rates for SMEs, stabilizing inflation, improving access to commercial bank credit, and strengthening macroeconomic fundamentals. These policy interventions are imperative to unlock the transformative potential of SMEs and ensure their sustained contribution to Nigeria's long-term economic development.

5.2 Policy Recommendations

Based on the results obtained, the following recommendations have been made:

Enhance Access to Affordable Credit for SMEs: The significant positive relationship between commercial bank credit and SME performance underscores the importance of accessible financing. Policymakers should strengthen existing credit guarantee schemes (e.g., CBN's SME Credit Guarantee Scheme) and incentivize commercial banks to develop tailor-made credit products for SMEs with lower collateral demands and longer tenures. Government can also support microfinance and development finance institutions to expand outreach to underserved SMEs.

Implement Targeted Interest Rate Concessions for Productive SMEs: Given the negative impact of high real interest rates on SMEs, there is a strong case for interest rate subsidies or differentiated interest regimes for

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productive SMEs, especially those in manufacturing, agriculture, and export-driven sectors. This can be achieved through interest drawback mechanisms or through directed lending policies under the supervision of the Central Bank of Nigeria.

Stabilize the Macroeconomic Environment and Control Inflation: The negative and significant effect of inflation on SME performance necessitates more coordinated fiscal and monetary policies to keep inflation within a manageable range. Price stability would not only reduce uncertainty for SMEs but also improve their planning and profitability. Policy tools should focus on controlling structural inflation by addressing supply-side bottlenecks such as energy costs and transport inefficiencies.

Mitigate Exchange Rate Volatility through Strategic Foreign Exchange Management: Although the exchange rate impact was found to be statistically insignificant, it remains economically relevant due to Nigeria's dependence on imports for SME inputs. To reduce this burden, the Central Bank should pursue a managed float regime with periodic interventions to avoid sharp currency devaluations. Additionally, promoting local content and backward integration can reduce SMEs' dependence on imported inputs and protect them from exchange rate shocks.

Rethink the Transmission Mechanism of Monetary Policy: The insignificant but conceptually important role of the monetary policy rate (MPR) suggests a weak transmission mechanism to the real sector, particularly SMEs. Policymakers should reevaluate how monetary policy changes are transmitted through the financial system and introduce complementary fiscal measures—such as tax reliefs and SME development funds to bridge the gap between policy intent and real economic outcomes.

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